

D1.1

version 2.0

Ethical Guidelines for the Living Labs

**Author(s): Katriina Soini, György Pataki, Mia Pihlajamäki,
Himansu S. Mishra, Ann Ojala and Juha Hiedanpää**

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No101084220. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Information about the deliverable

Project acronym	COEVOLVERS
Project full title	Coevolutionary approach to unlock the transformative potential of nature-based solutions for more inclusive and resilient communities
Grant Agreement no	101084220
Deliverable number	D1.1
Deliverable title	Ethical Guidelines for the Living Labs
Deliverable nature	Report
Dissemination level	Public
Work package and Task	WP1, Task 1.1
Contractual delivery date	30.04.2023
Actual delivery date	28.04.2023
Authors	Katriina Soini, György Pataki, Mia Pihlajamäki, Himansu S. Mishra, Ann Ojala and Juha Hiedanpää
Reviewers	The COEVOLVERS partners and the Ethical Advisor Markku Oksanen

Revision History

Version	Date	Author	Description
1.0	28.04.2024	Soini et al.	First version finalised
1.1	30.04.2024	Soini Katriina, Pihlajamäki Mia, Hiedanpää Juha	Annex V added
2.0.	14.11.2024	Soini Katriina, Ann Ojala, György Pataki	Chapter 3.4. on gender issues added. Ann Ojala added as co-author

Statement of originality: This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgment of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

How to quote this document: Soini, K., Pataki, G., Pihlajamäki, M., Mishra, H.S., and Hiedanpää, J., (2023) Ethical Guidelines for the Living Labs. COEVOLVERS D1.1

Executive summary

This report presents the ethical guidelines for the COEVOLVERS Living Labs to co-create NBS. The guidelines follow the overall principles of the COEVOLVERS -project aiming at making Nature-based Solutions (NBS) ethically more sensitive and inclusive contributing to the wellbeing of humans and nonhumans and to the adaptive resilience of their living environments (Chapter 2). The current EU and national level guidelines for ethical research and research integrity constitute the baseline for the work (Chapter 3). Given the broad geographical scope and diversity of the stakeholders and participants representing also marginalized and vulnerable groups and the aim to involve nonhuman perspective in the co-creation, specific situated ethical issues may arise. These issues were discussed and anticipated by COEVOLVERS partners in two workshops that focused particularly on the individual participants, living environments, the LL teams and researchers and the co-creation process (Chapter 4). Finally, procedures for monitoring and reporting the ethical issues during the project lifetime, and handling of problematic situations were set (Chapter 5). Templates for info sheet (Annex II), plain language statement and Consent form are provided in the ANNEX to be applied and used by the partners.

Table of contents

Executive summary	3
Table of contents.....	4
List of figures.....	5
1. Introduction	6
2. Perspective for ethics in COEVOLVERS	7
3. General ethical principles set by the European Commission and national ethics committees.....	9
3.1. Responsibilities of the researchers.....	10
3.2. Rights of the participants	11
3.3 Special considerations of individuals with limited capacity	12
3.3.1 Participation of minors.....	12
3.4. Gender aspects in Living Labs.....	13
3.4.1 Why should gender aspects need to be taken into account?	13
3.4.2. How should gender aspects be taken into account in the different parts and phases of the project?.....	14
4. Ethical principles in COEVOLVERS Living Labs.....	17
4.1 Actors in co-creation.....	17
4.2 Implications for the co-creation in COEVOLVERS Living Labs	19
I Individual participants.....	19
II Local community and living environment	21
III Living Lab teams and researchers	21
IV Co-creation process.....	22
4.3 How to facilitate ethical research practice during the research process? A practical guide for COEVOLVERS Living Labs.....	23
5. Ethical procedures to be applied in COEVOLVERS.....	28
5.1 COEVOLVERS Grant Agreement defining the basis for the procedures	28
5.2. Ethical Adviser	28
5.3. Transparency and accountability	29
5.4. Monitoring, assessment, and further development of ethical practices.....	29
ANNEXES:	31
ANNEX I: List of ethical codes and guidelines.....	31
ANNEX II Info sheet.....	34
ANNEX III. Plain language document.....	36
ANNEX IV. Consent form	38

ANNEX V: Follow-up on ethical issues (M6-M18) 39

List of figures

Figure 1. Inclusivity in co-creation of NBS in COEVOLVERS. 18
Figure 2. COEVOLVERS Living Labs 34

1. Introduction

Ethical aspects are integral for any type of research and the significance of ethical considerations cannot be understated especially in the realm of social science. It is incumbent upon individual researchers, research projects and academic or research institutions for ensuring that their research is responsible and complies with recognised ethical norms and guidelines established within the EU, the country and adopted by the institution. Research that concerns and engages humans, but also nonhumans¹ and the natural environment has special requirements to stay vigilant in addressing ethical concerns during and post-research activities.

COEVOLVERS, in collaboration with seven Living Labs, community of inquiry, across Europe, strives to co-create governance models, approaches and techniques for nature-based solutions (NBS) that will simultaneously benefit both humans and nature and promote the resilience of the socio-ecological communities and foster place-based sustainability transformation. The co-created solutions should consider the needs and concerns of those most affected by climate change, loss of biodiversity and post-pandemic recovery in their daily lives. COEVOLVERS' mission is thoroughly anchored on general ethical principles. COEVOLVERS Living Labs (LLs) bring together participants from local communities, organizations, government, companies, and research institutes participatory, transdisciplinary co-creation process in different social, political, and cultural contexts, and treats both human and nonhuman beings on equal terms. The process creates new relations between different actors, but also has impacts on involved individuals, communities, and the natural environment, and necessitates a thorough evaluation and consideration of all ethical aspects during the entirety of the co-creation process.

Given that the LLs operate within diverse social, political, and ecological contexts, both the co-creation processes and the co-created solutions inevitably raise case- and place-specific ethical issues. Ethical issues are inherently situational and relational, and often entail a degree of unpredictability with no single solution fitting all. Moreover, unforeseeable ethical issues may emerge. Thus, the responsible research principles need to be sensitive to the specifics of each case and situation.

This document outlines the baseline for a responsible and ethically sound research in COEVOLVERS (Chapter 3) and anticipates, potential case- and place-specific issues that may arise in the co-creation process in general and within the COEVOLVERS Living Labs in particular (see Chapters 2 and 4). These issues were identified and deliberated upon in two workshops. The first workshop was held on March 14th, 2023, and involved COEVOLVER partners and LL teams. As a result of the workshop, an initial list of ethical issues was compiled. The second workshop was held in Tartu on April 17th, 2023, and focused on deliberating in more detail selected ethical issues identified during the preparation of this document. These included 1) perspective for

¹ E.g. individual species, representatives of species, ecosystems, habitats, populations, physical structures, material substance. To be further specified in the project.

ethics in COEVOLVERS (Chapter 2); 2) positioning nonhumans in our research; 3) operationalizing co-creation; and 4) participation and their acknowledgement. In addition, a review of recent research on Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) was carried out to identify additional ethical issues, especially the key ethical considerations involved in working with both human and nonhuman entities and agencies. Although the review covered past and ongoing EU Horizon examples of NBS, it revealed a lack of focus on ethics related to nonhuman actors, which COEVOLVERS intends to address. Finally, we present a procedure, by which ethical guidelines will be monitored and assessed throughout the research process, address how emerging ethical issues will be handled in the COEVOLVERS project and outline how to respond to different ethical issues and conflicts (see Chapter 5).

2. Perspective for ethics in COEVOLVERS

“So it is best to think of moral progress as a matter of increasing sensitivity, increasing responsiveness to the needs of a larger and larger variety of people and things.”²

In COEVOLVERS, we study the socio-politics of nature-based solutions. The attempt is to rectify the equity-related design and implementation challenges to enable novel contributions to nature and people.

In COEVOLVERS, we have two ethical directions of growth: inward and outward. We have an ethical stance for our research activities, and we have an ethical stance that extends beyond our research practice. Our purpose is to provide conditions for COEVOLVERS’ moral progress and expand the moral sphere inwards towards the epistemic virtues of our own scientific practice and outward as increased sensitivity and responsiveness towards fellow humans, nonhumans, and the living environments of these people and other species. As important and relevant as general ethical principles are, ours is more of practices, and especially the practices of definition and co-creation of actual ethos of improvement.

Our cornerstone ethical concept is epistemic virtue. It refers to the ways in which we exercise science in connection with relevant scientific endeavours. Epistemic virtue refers to our attempt to accomplish what we have promised and assigned to do; that is, to make nature-based solutions ethically more sensitive and inclusive in contributing to the wellbeing of humans and nonhumans and to the adaptive resilience of their living environments. As Solomon³ put it: “But what is critical to an ethics of practice is not the absence of rules; it is rather the overriding importance of the concept of excellence or virtue (arete).” In this sense, our research aims for transdisciplinary excellence both in scientific practice and societal impact.

² Richard R. 1999. *Philosophy and social hope*. London: Penguin, p. 81

³ Solomon, R.C. 2003. *Living with Nietzsche*. Oxford: Oxford University Press, p. 122

COEVOLVERS approaches epistemic virtue by the means of transdisciplinary research. It helps us understand how we exercise science to change ecosocial circumstances persistently disconnecting human attention from other species and shared living environments. This approach of ours requires continuous reflexivity about problematic science-community-policy interfaces, and ethical sensitivity in co-creating nature-based solution and in implementing and evaluating them.

COEVOLVERS works in close collaboration with local humans, nonhumans, their communities and living environments. The research problem is always specified in close collaboration with those people and groups the research is executed together with. Often research methods are also explored, tested, and agreed upon together. The purpose is to come up with better problem definition⁴ and to derive practical reasons and workable tools for making things better⁵. COEVOLVERS works in belief that a practically and scientifically successful transdisciplinary research builds on the epistemic virtues of honesty (truthfulness), modesty, charity, and integrity⁶ and, as Misak⁷ would like to add, of humility.

All science well done may of course be epistemically virtuous, but transdisciplinary science differs from the normal science. COEVOLVERS' participatory research activity extends over the boundary of strict scientific procedures onto the implementation of findings and evaluation of their impacts. Humans, nonhumans, and their living environments are constitutive to the transdisciplinary research practice, they become partners, friends even, in scientific activities and in co-creation of concrete outcomes contributing to long-term wellbeing and flourishing.

COEVOLVERS operate in complex ethical situations. To address these problematic situations, Living Labs are operationalised as communities of inquiry. A community of inquiry is activated by problematic situations and organized to communicate and concretize the general purpose and objectives of co-creation and build commitment to achieve a well-functioning process for increased coevolutionary potential. Our Living Labs are our communities of inquiry and they also potentially welcome nonhuman actors as potential constituents.

COEVOLVERS will not only re-articulate the problematic situations in an everyday common language, but we will also expand the ways in which some concepts, metaphors, reasons, and phrases are used around these morally challenging situations to provide normative power and preparedness to act jointly to alleviate concrete challenges meeting primary, perhaps yet unknown needs and capabilities of life to our partners⁸.

⁴ Weston, A. 1992. Towards better problems. Temple University Press.

⁵ Liszka, J.J. 2021. Pragmatist ethics: a problem-based approach to what matters. Albany: State University of New York Press.

⁶ Talisse, R. 2005. Democracy after liberalism. London: Routledge, pp. 112-113

⁷ Misak, S. 2000. Truth, politics, and morality. London: Routledge, pp. 74

⁸ Brandom, R. 1994. Making it explicit. Boston: Harvard University Press; Nussbaum, M. 2011. Creating Capabilities: The Human Development Approach. Boston: Harvard University Press; Sen, A. 1999. Development as Freedom. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

The purpose of our collaboration and co-creation is to tie together epistemic virtues and moral ones: courageousness, temperance, playfulness, generosity, justice, and friendship grown along the transdisciplinary research process within and hopefully also between the communities of inquiry, Living Labs, encourage people to trustfully commit themselves to practical problem solving.

COEVOLVERS provides people with understanding about the socio-politics of nature-based solutions, practical reasons and workable means of rectifying design and implementation challenges. Along the research process, the Living Labs will grow a character of their own. In general, they will grow a character of morally sensitive and epistemically capable problem-solver and, in particular, they will come up with practical principles about how to adjust practices to make things better for humans and nonhumans while leaving no-one behind. This is the promise we made in our research proposal and that is the promise we are intended to keep by initiating our seven communities of inquiry, Living Labs.

3. General ethical principles set by the European Commission and national ethics committees

The COEVOLVERS project follows the ethical principles for research in social and human sciences set by the European Commission (EC) and national ethics committees and organisations. The aim is to ensure high-quality research with the highest standards of integrity and practice by committing to responsible science. Regarding the EC guidelines, the project follows particularly the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity⁹ and the Ethics in Social Sciences and Humanities¹⁰, which include the following principles for EU -funded research:

- respecting human dignity and integrity;
- ensuring honesty and transparency towards research subjects;¹¹
- respecting individual autonomy and obtaining free and informed consent (as well as assent whenever relevant);
- protecting vulnerable individuals;
- ensuring privacy and confidentiality;
- promoting justice and inclusiveness;
- minimising harm and maximising benefit;¹²

⁹ [ALLEA-European-Code-of-Conduct-for-Research-Integrity-2017.pdf](#)

¹⁰ Ethics in Social Sciences and Humanities. European Commission. European Commission, 2021. [ethics-in-social-science-and-humanities_he_en.pdf \(europa.eu\)](#)

¹¹ COEVOLVERS prefer the term “participants”.

¹² COEVOLVERS acknowledge that “benefits” and “harms” may hold different meanings in various societies and for various people. Harming for example may simply refer to something bad, as “harming nature”, which is a moral issue. The harm-benefit may also be seen from the utilitarian perspective and easily translate into cost-benefit analysis, which can imply certain interests and behaviours that may harm society. Moral growth, instead, involves different parties considering the harm and benefits to others, extending beyond utilitarianism. When

- sharing the benefits with disadvantaged populations;
- respecting and protecting the environment and future generations.

In addition, the project partners follow the ethical standards established by their national ethical committees/organisations and when applicable, their respective institutions (Annex I). The following sub-chapters (3.1-3.3) provide some examples of general principles for conducting research in social sciences and humanities, based on the Ethical Principles of Research with Human Participants provided by Finnish Advisory Board on Research Integrity (see the full document here¹³). These examples focus on the responsibilities of the researchers (3.1), the rights of participants (3.2), and special considerations relating to the participation of individuals with limited capacity (3.3) and minors (3.3.1). These examples aim to complement and enrich the EC's ethical principles listed above and can be used as general guidelines by the project partners. However, as the national guidelines may vary to a certain degree, **the partner organizations are responsible for following primarily the ethical codes and guidelines of their respective countries and institutions.**

3.1. Responsibilities of the researchers

The Finnish Advisory Board on Research Integrity identifies the responsibilities of the researchers in research with human participants the following way (please note that these principles may vary to some extent between the ethical guidelines of each LL/COEVOLVERS country and the institute leading the LL. Bolding added by the authors):

- **respecting the dignity and autonomy of human¹⁴ research participants.** These ethical concerns include the right to life, personal liberty and integrity, freedom of movement, freedom of religion and conscience, freedom of expression, protection of property and the right to privacy.
- **respecting material and immaterial cultural heritage of the indigenous people.** Indigenous people have the right to maintain and develop their own language and culture.
- **not causing significant risks, damage or harm to research participants, communities or other subjects of research.**
- **collecting informed consents,** From the participants, who should be fully informed about the goals and objectives, the purpose and scope of the project, and regarding any associated potential risks or benefits that are expected

considering moral growth, we should evaluate how harm and benefits are assessed, whether from an internal or external perspective. For COEVOLVERS, this might encourage a positive change in attitude.

¹³ The ethical principles of research with human participants and ethical review in the human sciences in Finland. Finnish National Board on Research Integrity. TENK publications. 3/2019

¹⁴ The Finnish Advisory Board on Research Integrity does not address the ethical issues relating to the inclusion of nonhumans *as participants* in participatory research per se, but the topic is addressed by the COEVOLVERS project in sub-chapter 3.2 (footnote 12) and in Chapter 4.

thereof. The informed consent of participants will be collected before participation.

- **ensuring data privacy and data protection-** If the research includes collection, storage, and use of personal data, which is subject to important ethical considerations, individual's privacy rights are respected, and their data is protected from unauthorised access or use. The personal data will be collected, stored, and used in a manner that complies with privacy laws and regulations (GDPR, EU, <https://gdpr.eu/what-is-gdpr/>) and protects the privacy of individuals. In case of collecting and processing sensitive personal and environmental data, the data is collected and processed transparently and securely and that participants will be fully informed about how their data will be used and protected.

3.2. Rights of the participants

According to the Finnish Advisory Board on Research Integrity, the participants have right to

- **receive an understandable and truthful view of the aims of the research and any potential harm and risks.** The research participant must be given an accurate account of the effects and potential benefits of the research.
- **be aware that they are participating in research, especially in situations in which the researcher is in a role other than that of a researcher in relation to the participant.** The researcher also informs the research participant of other affiliations relevant to the research.
- **receive information on the content of the research, the processing of personal data and how the research will be conducted in practice, such as what participation in the research means, and what kind of lifespan has been envisaged for processing and preserving the research data.** Whenever possible, information is given in a language that the participant understands, in writing or in electronic form. The research participant must be given sufficient time to consider their decision whether to participate, and any questions they have regarding the research must be answered.
- **be able to participate on a voluntary basis and to refuse or withdraw participation at any time.** The research participant must not feel that participation is compulsory or feel afraid of negative consequences if they refuse to participate in the research. The researcher documents the participant's consent to participate in the research, either orally, in writing, electronically or by other means. They may withdraw from the research

or an individual phase of the research permanently or for a temporary period.

3.3 Special considerations of individuals with limited capacity ¹⁵

The Finnish Advisory Board on Research Integrity highlights that there are some special requirements concerning people with impaired capacity. Human capacity can be constrained for various reasons. Nonetheless, physical and sensory impairments or advanced age do not inherently restrict one's right of autonomy, nor do they impede the right to decide whether to participate in research. The principles on people with limited capacity entail that

- People with limited capacity are informed about the research **in a way that they are able to understand.**
- Even if their participation in the research requires the approval of a legal representative, **the person with limited capacity primarily gives their consent to participate in the research themselves.**
- Researchers **respect the autonomy of research participants with limited capacity and the principle of voluntary participation, irrespective of whether the consent of the legal representative has been obtained for the research.** If participating in the research is not in the best interests of a person with limited capacity and if they do not wish to participate in the research, the researcher must discontinue the person's participation.
- People who, owing to a mental health disorder, a developmental disorder or other similar reason, do not have the capacity to give their consent to research can be defined as being unable to consent (e.g., in the Finnish Medical Research Act (488/1999)).

3.3.1 Participation of minors

Minors must be informed about the research and should be communicated in a manner that they can understand. Similarly, to other principles, the specific ethical requirements relating to, for example, minors' age, may vary between the ethical guidelines of each LL country and the research institute leading the LL.

- If the minor is **above a certain age, their own consent may be sufficient for participation in the research.** The parent or carer may need to be informed of

¹⁵ While the Finnish Advisory Board on Research Integrity does not address the ethical issues relating to the inclusion of nonhumans as participants in participatory action research/co-creation, the COEVOLVERS project notes that in animals rights literature, the approach to nonhumans could be informed by the same principles as those relating to human individuals with limited capacity (sub-chapter 3.3).

the research also in these situations if the research design or research questions permit it.

- The participation of younger minors **under a certain age is primarily decided by the parent or carer**. Informing the parent or carer is also sufficient in research that does not involve the processing of the personal data of the minor participant (for example observation without recording devices and processing of personal data).
- Even if participation in the research requires the approval of the parent or carer or a legal representative, **minors also give their own consent** to participating in the research.
- Researchers must always respect the autonomy of minor research participants and the principle of voluntary participation, irrespective of whether the consent of the parent or carer has been obtained for the research.

3.4. Gender aspects in Living Labs

In this chapter we discuss, why and how gender aspects should be taken into account in the Living Lab activities. First, it should be understood that the terms sex and gender are not synonyms. Sex refers to the biological differences between males and females. Gender refers to the continuum of complex psychosocial self-perceptions, attitudes, and expectations people have about members of both sexes. (see [Gender in EU research and innovation](#)). It goes beyond the traditional binary view of men and women, as it encompasses a spectrum of identities, that are influenced by social, cultural, and personal factors. Even the terms male and female, man and woman are not interchangeable: to be male or female originates from physical characteristics derived from sex chromosomes and genes, while being a man or a woman holds broader meaning, with cultural concepts of masculinity and femininity coming into play.

3.4.1 Why should gender aspects need to be taken into account?

From the point of view of EU, gender dimension plays a vital role in research and innovation as it is expected to allow to address the diverse needs of EU citizens (see [Gender in EU research and innovation](#)). (Gender in EU research and innovation). Including a gender perspective in research, thus, may enhance the societal relevance of the knowledge, technologies and innovations produced, and contribute to production of greater goods and services. Besides these general, EU research driven reasons, gender aspects are important for the COEVOLVERS Living Labs due to our research topic and work with the local communities:

- The ultimate aim of the COEVOLVERS work is to provide tools and techniques for NBS design and implementation that would lead to community resilience. This aim implies that gender aspects need to be considered in both design and implementation of NBS. In many countries, men tend to hold dominant roles in areas related to NBS design and implementation, such as land ownership, business leadership, and decision-making positions, in topics which COEVOLVERS are examining in the Living Labs.
- Acknowledging gender aspects would not only improve the quality of the LL activities, but also provide valuable and relevant insights for inclusive NBS design and implementation. Furthermore, considering gender dimension in the LL activities and research can prompt new socially relevant research questions for NBS design and implementation and beyond.
- Finally, through the LL work, addressing the gender aspects in and through the LL activities in an appropriate way may strengthen the overall inclusivity of different groups in the local communities. On the other hand, failing to address these issues in an appropriate way may in the worst case aggravate gender and other social or cultural disparities in the local community.

3.4.2. How should gender aspects be taken into account in the different parts and phases of the project?

In first place, Living Labs should follow in their activities the European wide gender equality policies (see the list below). Besides EU Policy aspects, partner organizations have their gender equality policies, which the respective Living Lab should be aware of and follow. In general, two main aspects regarding gender issues can be discerned:

- *Gender as a dimension in research* means taking into account the possible differences between male and female/ men and women (biological characteristics as well as the social and cultural features), and sensitivity to different genders, in the content of the project. Integrating gender dimension is a mandatory requirement in all research and innovation projects across Horizon Europe, unless a topic explicitly specifies otherwise.
- *Gender balance* refers to the balance between women and men in research teams who implement a project. Horizon Europe projects should aim to have an even, 50/50 participation rate of both men and women amongst teams and in leading roles.

A European project Equal4Europe has provided a Handbook for Gender Equality plans (2023) to be applied in the research, and a check list for Gender equality policy (see: <https://equal4europe.eu/checklist-for-gender-sensitive-research/>). In the following we elaborate against this check list the most essential gender aspects to be considered by the COEVOLVERS Living Labs:

- Co-creation activities (Tasks 1.3.; 1.4.; 3.1.; 4.3): In order to empower LL participants through principles of gender mainstreaming, the aim is to consider the needs and perspectives of all genders in the co-creation, when possible. Thus, the participatory co-creation activities in the LLs should be planned in a way that accessibility and processes take into account the gender aspects in order to ensure that everyone has an equal opportunity to participate regardless of the gender.
- Collecting and analyzing data (Tasks 3.2.;3.3., 3.4.; 4.2.; 5.2.; 5.3): Together with the respective Task leaders LL Teams are responsible for conducting the questionnaires, surveys, focus groups, experiments in a way that they are aware of hidden assumptions and disclose potentially relevant sex and /or gender differences in the data. Furthermore, operationalization of the research in form of collecting the data or interacting with participants should consider special gender-related needs, behaviors, attitudes and lifestyles. In the analysis of the data, LL teams together with the respective Task leaders should consider including gender aspects in the analysis especially if the data concerns attitudes, values, behaviors, needs or decision making. It is also good to consider also whether analysing data separately for women and men might bring new information.
- Outputs and impact of the research (Tasks 2.4.; 4.4.; 5.4; 5.5.): Overall, co-creation and research carried out in the LLs should be open to a possibility for different outcomes and impacts on all genders. Furthermore, especially concerning the design of the final outputs like toolkit, handbook and policy briefs, the gender dimension should be considered as an aspect of co-evolutionary approach and inclusive NBS design and implementation.
- Communication (all LLs, and all WPs and Tasks throughout the project): Language can be regarded as a reflection of reality, but also constructing it. In the LL communication language used should be gender and sex sensitive, not to bring any harm to any gender or sex. On the other hand, gender aspects should also be brought forth, when appropriate concerning the issue in question. WP6 has a role in giving training and guidelines in these issues specific to our project, and there are general guidelines available for gender sensitive communication in research and academia, for example [A gender-sensitive communication A resource for policymakers, legislators, media and anyone else with an interest in making their communication more inclusive.](#)
- Management (Tasks 1.3; Task 5.1. WP7): Sex/gender balance should be a criteria, when establishing Living Lab core-groups and National Consultation groups, or any other group or team within/by a Living Lab or at the project level. The Living Lab teams as well as the consortium as a whole should also aim for a gender balance in its composition.

In the first place LLs are expected to follow these guidelines (that are also valid throughout the Chapter 4), as well as to seek for further information for example from

the resources listed below. These guidelines will be presented in one of the forthcoming Living Lab meetings. However, there might be questions, which are specific to the LL, topic of the project or certain research method. In these cases will be discussed separately between the respective Task Leader and LL team, and at the project level, when necessary. We may also consider consulting our Ethical Advisor or Advisory board members, who have experience in these issues.

More information can be found available here:

[Gendered Innovations 2: How inclusive analysis contributes to research and innovation.](#) European Commission, 2020.

[What is the gender dimension in research? Case studies in interdisciplinary research.](#) Korsvik, T.R. & Rustad, L.M., 2018.

[Gendered Research: Integrating sex and gender analysis into the research process.](#) LERU (League of European Research Universities), 2015.

[Gendered Innovations: How gender analysis contributes to research.](#) European Commission, 2013.

[Toolkit: Gender in EU-funded research.](#) European Commission, 2011.

[Gendered Innovations:](#) practical methods of sex and gender analysis, and case studies illustrating how sex and gender analysis leads to innovation.

[Sida's Gender Toolbox:](#) knowledge, tools and inspiration on how to operationalise gender equality, gender analysis and gender mainstreaming.

[European Institute for Gender Equality:](#) information on gender challenges in 19 policy areas, ranging from fisheries to culture. Also offers methods and tools to address these challenges, including gender analysis, gender stakeholder consulting, sex-disaggregated data and good practice examples.

[EQUAL4EUROPE Gender Equality Plans for Social Sciences, Business & Management schools:](#) Checklist for Gender-Sensitive Research.

[Developing gender-sensitive value chains:](#) an e-Course from FAO on addressing gender dimensions in value chain interventions in the agricultural sector.

4. Ethical principles in COEVOLVERS Living Labs

The previous chapter describes the general ethical principles identified by the EU and national ethical committees/organisations in the research in social sciences and humanities. In this chapter, we present the results of two COEVOLVERS ethics workshops where additional ethical issues (potentially) relevant for Living Labs were identified and discussed.

4.1 Actors in co-creation

COEVOLVERS will co-create Nature-based governance models and techniques in and for different social and political contexts. COEVOLVERS understand nature-based solutions (NBS), as co-created by humans and nonhumans, shaping long-term co-evolution of nature and people benefitting some elements of both in economically reasonable and innovative ways to address sustainability challenges. Co-creation is widely used in both scientific literature and in the vocabulary of enterprises and businesses. In this document co-creation refers to a process where a particular group of people (including scientists) engage in deliberating on shared understandings of needed change, developing novel ideas, knowledge and the means of intervention into the social-ecological systems for improvement, and following and reacting to the outcomes and impacts of these actions.

Co-creation is based on a principle of transdisciplinary and transformative research practice aiming for societal change. Co-creation aims for improved understanding and through social learning, changes in the situation or field of inquiry, but also fostering community participation and individual empowerment to enhance societal change. The co-creative process itself can be seen as a form of co-evolution since the outcomes of co-creation may have unintended consequences that go beyond the immediate goals. By fostering co-creation, we may achieve objectives that were not initially anticipated.

Co-creation can be characterised as an open and iterative process composed of different cycles including planning, acting observing, reflecting, and involving all kinds of actors on equal terms in the process. Co-creation is qualitatively different from having actors from outside academia only responding and reacting to the research conducted. Different types of ethical issues may arise during the different cycles emerging from or concerning participation of individual actors (humans and nonhumans), local communities and their living environments, Living Lab leaders and researchers and their institutions, as well as the co-creation process itself. (See Figure 1.)

Figure 1. Inclusivity in co-creation of NBS in COEVOLVERS.

The individual actors participating in the co-creation may represent, on one hand, those who can contribute to the solutions or solution options, and those who are somehow impacted by the research or solutions co-created. The participants may include human participants representing communities (citizens), representatives of NGOs, governmental organisations and companies and researchers, and nonhuman participants. They may have different roles in the co-creation process: some of them can actively participate in the planning and design of the co-creation process (members of the ‘core group’), while some others may contribute to the different activities. The individual participants are part of the wider local

communities and their embedded living environment with different social, cultural, political, and ecological features.

In COEVOLVERS -project also **the nonhumans** (e.g., individual species, representatives of species, ecosystems, habitats, populations, physical structures, material substance) are considered as participants in the co-creation. Although discussion around the ethics in multispecies is now booming and different ways to address these issues are presented, clear ethical guidelines that consider nonhumans as participants are lacking, compared to research where nonhumans or multispecies communities are somehow objects of research using invasive methods. Furthermore, at this point it is not clear the whole variety of nonhumans will be involved in the COEVOLVERS -project besides for example the sheep in the Catalonia Living Lab or the different types of ecosystems of the Living Lab. Therefore, situated ethics is needed in mapping out the various responsibilities and practices related to nonhumans. This can be realised, for example, by engaging representatives of nonhumans (e.g., environmental NGOs and local people) and continuously assessing potential impacts of our actions to nonhumans and avoiding negative ones. In addition, the COEVOLVERS will also actively search for other methods for representation and participation of nonhumans from the literature and consider using them in the LLs.

Ideally, **LL teams and researchers** often have a key role, at least a facilitator or mediator in the co-creation process. All Living Labs leaders have background in research, although they may act in LLs in multiple other roles. Their actions are affected by the roles they take in the co-creation as well as the disciplines and institutes they are representing as well as the wider social-political systems. LL teams as well as other COEVOLVERS researchers may also be part of the of the local communities or living environments of the respective LLs.

4.2 Implications for the co-creation in COEVOLVERS Living Labs

In the following we will describe shortly key ethical issues that need to be acknowledged in the co-creation with each of the aforementioned actor groups, followed by the special remarks and suggestions by the COEVOLVERS raised in the two workshops. These lists are not meant to be exhaustive or final checklists to be followed, but rather aiming at making more tangible the possible ethical aspects and situations that may arise during the co-creation process.

I Individual participants

Inclusion of human and nonhuman actors: Co-creation typically involves a wide range of stakeholders, including citizens, representatives of local communities, NGOs, government agencies, and private sector organisations and having different social, economic, cultural backgrounds and position in the society, as well as individual species, representatives of species, ecosystems and substance. COEVOLVERS have identified the following special necessities:

- Carefully think about all types of actors that should be invited to co-creation activities;
- Consider, who can represent various minor and people with limited capacity;
- Reduce adverse procedures for marginal people;
- Pay particular attention to those interested in the nonhuman side (nature) and in environmental education;
- Consider the difference between equality and equity: do we treat all the actors equally, or recognize different starting points by idea of equity, and target special affirmative actions/proposals to vulnerable groups;
- Be aware of the possible power structures in hierarchical organisations/systems;
- Consider starting with small group to ensure safe environment, later open up more;
- Consider accessibility of the language and communication including
 - different language(s);
 - the use of technology, time, and resources for communication considering e.g., elderly people;
 - avoid scientific jargon.

In addition to the abovementioned principles and practices on engaging nonhuman participants (see sub-chapters 3.3 and 4.1), the following special requirements were identified by the COEVOLVERS:

- Acknowledge the inclusion of nonhumans is particularly important for younger people and for the future of local communities
- Consider, who could represent nonhumans in the LL activities, but also how nonhumans could be represented (or considered); Investigate what kind of mechanisms exist for the inclusion of nonhumans?

- Be aware of potential conflicts between different people and nonhuman entities or their representatives which may arise from the factors such as conflicting interests or perceptions of human actors on COEVOLVERS approach to nonhumans;
- Recognise and address imbalances in ways how the different nonhuman actors are represented and valued (e.g., charismatic vertebrates compared to insects of fungi);
- Raise the level of awareness among citizens regarding the sensitivity and activities of nonhuman entities that may cause destruction and disruption.

Diversity of the participants, vulnerable and marginalised participants: Inclusivity in the research means involvement of diverse people, who may represent a stakeholder group or themselves, and are in different social, economic position and having diverse cultural background and different capacities due to various deprivations, health issues, differently abled or experiencing limited mobility. There might be people, who are or may feel excluded from the mainstream social, economic and/or cultural life due to race, gender identity, sexual orientation, age, physical ability, language, and/or immigration status. In principle COEVOLVERS will have equal or neutral approach to all individuals or groups of actors avoiding deliberate neglect of some groups/individuals. In addition, the researchers should

- be respectful terms when referring to different actors;
- avoid words that include sensitive information or refer to reasons for vulnerability or marginalisation and try to find alternative wording when needed (e.g., less-resilient communities/fringe communities/underprivileged groups/disadvantaged groups)
- be sensitive when using terms vulnerable and especially marginalised, avoid labelling and any word relating to being poor or in poverty;
- acknowledge and be prepared to handle possible tensions and power imbalances especially between actors having different social, economic and cultural background;
- choose between equality and equity, i.e. treat all the actors equally and recognize different starting points by idea of equity and targeting special affirmative actions/proposals to vulnerable groups.

Autonomy of the participants. Participants can make his or her own decisions about what to do and what to agree to in the co-creation process.

- recall that participation is voluntary, and the participants have a right to withdraw from the participation for any reasons; explain also how to withdraw and when;
- participants have right to take part in those activities they are willing to;
- pay special attention to the autonomy of people with limited capacities, minors and nonhumans.

II Local community and living environment

Responsiveness to local needs and conditions: Public perception, demand and future priorities connected to the living environment of the local actors are crucial to any project that deals with alteration, improvement or, in general, working with local culture and nature towards addressing social, ecological, technological and governance issues. COEVOLVERS pay attention to the following principles related to responsiveness to local needs and conditions:

- recall that the project is designed to support local needs and problems;
- the vision or goal for the area/community/LL should be a product of co-creation;
- be aware of the character and values of the local ecological system.

Social, cultural, economic, political and ecological impact of the co-creation: COEVOLVERS -project aims at flourishing, having a positive social, cultural and environmental impact, including the effects on employment, local economies, community well-being, social cohesion and active living opportunities, but also the relations of between the humans and between humans and nonhumans. Co-creation may have also adverse impacts on the social-ecological community. COEVOLVERS sees it important to

- make people aware that there will be various impacts;
- avoid harm with our activities to nature and nonhumans;
- identify potential negative the impacts to avoid adverse impacts on local community and their living environment;
- consider the impacts' implications for social equity and ensure that the benefits and costs are distributed fairly;
- in case of impact assessment, participants/actors involved in the LL should be involved and identify the main principles guiding such assessments;
- be aware of the potential conflicts with institutional management and governance systems in place.

III Living Lab teams and researchers

Different roles of the LL teams and researchers. LL leaders and researchers may have different roles in the collaborative research and LL activities, like external observer; facilitator, mediator or knowledge broker.

- be explicit about your role(s) in the research aware that the problem of diverse roles (e.g., co-researcher and facilitator) may raise and have concerns for research quality and confidentiality;
- avoid taking a side in communication and engagements in respect to different interest groups in LL;
- communicate clearly and openly regarding the roles of LL team members/researchers.

Reflection and (self-)reflexivity. The Living Lab teams and the researchers need to be reflective about their own normative, value-based, beliefs and aims shaping the research process. Researchers should also consider their role and position in the

research. This kind of self-reflexion of one's own judgements and practices helps identify personal beliefs or attitudes that may influence the activities in the project. Researcher is also an individual subject to various harms in participatory research. They must have sufficient knowledge and skills to conduct it.

IV Co-creation process

General principles: Co-creation is essentially a collaborative activity and participation should be based on equal and voluntary participation:

- Recall that co-creation is based on voluntary participation and avoid forcing activities;
- Priorities of researchers and LL participants – what do we all want to get out of it;
- Be explicit about what kind of information will be collected, how and for which purpose, and how the data will be managed and used;
- Be clear whether and to which extent the project is a research project and what our role is supporting local communities and vulnerable actors. In the latter case consider participants as equal collaborators and avoid terms and practices that may make them feel like objects of the research;
- Consider, what we give back to actors;
- Be aware of the different power imbalances and potential conflicts;
- Be prepared for the unexpected.

Research methods: In general, the research methods must be selected in a way that enables equal participation and do not risk the participants' health, autonomy or integrity. The following aspects were raised:

- Select participatory methods that can facilitate active involvement of all types of actors (also the quieter ones) in LL meetings and activities;
- Engage actors in planning the activities to facilitate their participation in the actual doing;
- Stakeholder analysis tool inclusive for nonhumans may help to identify vulnerable and missing actors;
- Consider equality vs equity in fieldwork strategy and using affirmative methods;
- Physical activity can promote active participation in and experience of nature;
- Goals of the activity will be developed according to participants needs and resources;
- Design workshops that capture participants views;
- Find ways to involve those who are not so active on personal workshops;
- Backwards translation: use the language of LL team to revise and develop the concepts used in the project.

Privacy: Further, the core theme of ethics should be the right to privacy, participation in decision-making processes, and free, prior and informed consent (ANNEX III and IV.). Within COEVOLVER, it is important to ensure that the privacy of these

communities is respected and that they are consulted and involved in the design and implementation of Living Labs.

- Ensure anonymity of the participants when disseminating LL results;
- Consider question of identifiability of institution;
- Anonymise captured dialogue to give people the ability to join in without fear of being identified;
- Informed and reasoned consent as an ongoing process (procedural consent).

Acknowledgement of participation: Acknowledging that participants give their time, knowledge and other efforts to research projects, researchers should compensate for the participants to avoid one-way extraction of resources. You may consider the following aspects related to the acknowledgement of participation:

- Formal recognition (such as certificate or letter of thanks) for supporting the research knowledge of participants and contributors should be respected as valid ways of knowing;
- An acknowledgement of contributors in citations or as authors or as contributors in publications if the co-authorship is not a case;
- Issues related to data ownership and intellectual property. Data ownership and intellectual property issues need to be discussed with involved partners. Ownership over the collected data or expect to have influence on how it is used and shared. Owning data may also be a legal question.
- While it can be fair to compensate for participants' time and efforts, questions arise: What is a person compensated for? Should all the participants receive the same compensation? Does the compensation affect the co-creative research process? Does the compensation affect collected data? These aspects must be carefully considered.

Sustainability of the NBS: The solution co-created by COEVOLVERS should maximise the benefits and avoid harms to individual human and nonhuman actors to the local communities and the living environment individual human and nonhuman actors in the long-term. It is possible that despite efforts there will be trade-offs between the individuals and within the members of the local communities.

- The trade-offs and sustainability related to co-created NBS should be anticipated through with participatory monitoring and evaluation during the process.

4.3 How to facilitate ethical research practice during the research process? A practical guide for COEVOLVERS Living Labs

In this chapter, we give some practical guidelines and tips on how the general ethical principles mentioned above can be operationalized in the different phases of the project¹⁶.

Research Planning & Throughout the Research

- *Consider involvement (who-how-when) and compensation of participants* - Researchers should be reflective on their research design choices whether and how they might create inclusion and exclusion for the diverse stakeholder they want to engage with as co-researchers. Inviting participants (as co-researchers) to the research requires careful thinking and iterative steps. Not all participants (and group of actors) are ready to participate at the very beginning of a research. Their needs and expectations should be learnt and responded to. Furthermore, their time and resources invested in the research should be acknowledged and compensated for in ways that fits their expectations and the possibilities of the research project. To make justice to their contributions is highly important in a research based on co-creation and wider stakeholder participation.
- *Reflect on how your research design can create vulnerability?* - While the language used by researchers should be very sensitive and reflective upon avoiding creating feelings of disempowerment and vulnerability, there are concerns related to the research design that researchers should self-critically examine. It might be argued that we are all vulnerable and the research design should be created and reflected upon to avoid creating vulnerabilities to any parties in the research process. The research design choices might contribute to feelings of disempowerment and make certain groups of participants voiceless if not carefully reflected upon. Moreover, researchers themselves might become vulnerable if the research design is not discussed, appropriate training and supervision are not provided.
- *Co-created data, knowledge, impacts (who owns?)* - It is important to be open to discuss “ownership” issues in a participatory research process. It is a crucial power issue but also a concern for acknowledgement and compensation that who owns the data and knowledge generated in the research? How the needs of co-researchers in this regard are taken due concern and they feel empowered and appropriately treated? Moreover, the research potential impacts should be reflected upon since all participatory research is an intervention in others’ life and influence their life chances.

¹⁶ Based on Thompson, A.R. and Chambers, E. (2011) Ethical Issues in Qualitative Mental Health Research. In: Harper, D. and Thompson, A.R. (Eds.) *Qualitative Research Methods in Mental Health and Psychotherapy: A Guide for Students and Practitioners*. Chapter 3, pp. 23-37. Wiley, Print ISBN:9780470663738 |Online ISBN:9781119973249 |DOI:10.1002/9781119973249

- *Awareness & training (how to build rapport, how to manage affect, etc.)* -All researchers and co-researchers may need to receive training and need discussions at different stages and steps of the research process to be prepared and avoid any harm to others as well as themselves.
- *Writing reflective research diary & providing supervision to researchers* - Among other possibilities, there are two tools that help self-critical reflection and awareness for avoiding harm that it is relatively easy to embed in any research process. Writing self-reflective diary is a way of systematising emotions and feelings inevitably emerging in any research. Providing supervision for researchers and co-researchers as necessary is also a valuable source for self- and group-level reflection while provides important emotional support to the participants.
- *Consider how to enter & leave the field* – Entering and leaving the research field is not only an important research strategic concern but it involves emotions and concerns for justice and power. Ethical reflection is seriously needed prior to entering and leaving decisions beyond both significant research design issues.

Recruitment/engagement

- *Consider factors influencing voluntary consent and power imbalances* – There are already existing power relations and structures when the researchers enter the field. The existing power relations and structures will also influence the options for actors to voluntarily join or reject joining a research process. It is important therefore that researchers carefully approach the issue of recruitment and engagement of diverse participants avoiding doing harm to any of them.
- *Check out potential participants' assumptions about research in advance and ensure awareness of roles in collaborative research* – When entering the field, researchers bring all the existing social stereotypes and usual expectations of the specific societal context. In the case of participatory and co-creative research, it is important to learn participants' expectations from research in a dialogical process in order to minimise the risks of potential mismatches among researchers' and participants' expectations.
- *Facilitate understanding of the nature, purpose, consequences of research and providing multiple opportunities* – Gaining participants' informed consent for taking part in the research is not one time issue in a co-creative and participatory research process. Since a participatory research design should accommodate and respond to emerging issues by modifying the research design, gaining informed consent is a processual issue and should be treated as such throughout the research process.

Data Collection

- *Discuss confidentiality & privacy* – While protecting confidentiality and privacy in a research process enjoys general guidance from research ethics codes, there is always a need in participatory research to provide space for discussing these issues and learn about the potential special needs and expectations of participants. This is very important from participants' self-determination point of view and, moreover, to avoid any harm that might happen due to context specificities and participants' characteristics.
- *Facilitate understanding dual roles (practitioner & researcher)* – Dual roles always bring new, sometimes, unwanted, ethical challenges. They will clearly influence the role of researchers and the quality of research data. It is of high significance to ethically reflect upon the potential challenges and moral dilemmas that may arise from dual roles in the field, otherwise research integrity might be seriously suffer.
- *Empower participants to have control for terminating data collection* – While from a narrow research perspective it is always a loss when participants leave the collaborative process, however, this should be considered normal and even an important component of voluntariness. The research design should provide participants a safe space for their right to withdraw at any point of the research process without any harm and discomfort.
- *Spend appropriate time with participants* - While this is a conventional expectation from field research for the sake of collecting high quality research data, it also involves an important ethical approach: learning the perspective of participants in order to make justice to their understanding and show respect for their engagement.

Data Analysis

- *Data analysis co-created?* - In participatory research, it is always an issue whether co-researchers participate in data analysis and how? While in general it is an important step to enhance the empowerment potential and participatory quality of the research if data analysis is also a co-creation process, it raises challenges to confidentiality of research participants. Therefore, the choice of a co-created data analysis should be reflected upon and designed in a way of avoiding harm and breaking confidentiality to research participants.
- *Ensure interpretations are grounded in participants' accounts* - If data analysis wants to avoid doing harm to research participants, an important way of doing so is ensuring that analysis and interpretation of data is grounded in a deep

understanding of the field. This does not mean to abandon a critical perspective but should be practised in order to avoid any potential harm to research participants.

- *Facilitate dialogue on what will be like for participants to read research reports ?* - Avoiding harm to research participants as a very basic ethical principle should also be reflected regarding research outputs. Among the usual research outputs, research reports are usually produced by professional researchers. However, it is important to think whether research reports are understandable to research participants since they are significant actors in these reports and co-producers of the knowledge included. To generate and facilitate a dialogue with research participants on the nature and qualities of research reports, or any other significant research outputs, is a significant moral step to avoid any potential harms to participants.

Dissemination

- *Enhance anonymity* – Any dissemination activities should keep the confidentiality and privacy of research participants. It is useful to discuss with research participants in what language to be used and in what ways the context and their roles can be interpreted and communicated to wider audiences.
- *Provide feedback in an accessible fashion and in a way that is useful to participants* – Since research is always a knowledge-generation process, it is a research design issue what kind of ways are appropriate for participants to enhance their learning from feedback and research outputs. It is significant from a power perspective that research design supports the understanding of all participants and the empowerment of less powerful participants.
- *Gain participants' views on the collaborative research process* - Participatory research provides significant learning opportunities and critical self-reflection for researchers particularly if it is carefully designed into the research as appropriate feedback from co-researchers. It is a major learning point also for ethical reflection and researchers' ethical self-development.

5. Ethical procedures to be applied in COEVOLVERS

5.1 COEVOLVERS Grant Agreement defining the basis for the procedures

COEVOLVERS consortium works in compliance with the ethical principles and the applicable EU, international, and national laws for the ethical issues identified in the Ethics Summary Report, and any additional problems that may emerge during the grant will be ensured. The Consortium also confirms that the guidance provided in the European Commission Ethics Self-Assessment Guidelines¹⁷ will be rigorously followed for any applicable ethics issue.

The ethical principles and preliminary guidelines for COEVOLVERS developed together with the project partners and presented in this document will be reflected by the Living Labs and developed as refinements concerning the specific issues regarding each of the LL to create a safe environment for collaboration. The academic and practice partners will ensure that no discriminatory practices or unfair treatment occurs and will apply all necessary measures to protect the vulnerable people and minimise the risk of their stigmatisation.

Guidelines for ethics in data collection (including the special needs related to the digital tools), data management concerning various groups, considering especially the requirements of the vulnerable groups are provided in Data Management Plan (D 6.1.). The data and information that the Living Lab participants will be requested to provide will vary according to the specific objectives of the tasks in WP3–WP5. In WP3 data on the values, motives and beliefs will be collected through interviews, functional group discussions, national survey and social media. In WP4, the assessment of human marginalisation and vulnerability in NBS governance will be conducted by the general public pool and interviews. WP5 will carry out a co-productive process with creative methodologies to co-produce a range of tools that support more inclusive NBS, e.g., participatory mapping and world café sessions. Dissemination, exploitation and communication work package (WP6) will create a responsible communication consent and guidelines for communication about the vulnerable individuals and groups at the start of the COEVOLVERS project.

5.2. Ethical Adviser

The Ethical Adviser, Senior Lecturer Markku Oksanen, University of Eastern Finland, (1.1.2023 - 27.9.2024) and Researcher, PhD Mikko Puumala (7.10.2024 onwards) will oversee and assist the handling of ethics issues that emerge during the research process. He will pay a particular attention to the involvement of children, fringe

¹⁷ How to complete your ethics self-assessment. European Commission, 2021. [how-to-complete-your-ethics-self-assessment_en.pdf \(europa.eu\)](https://ec.europa.eu/easip/en/how-to-complete-your-ethics-self-assessment_en.pdf)

communities (vulnerable groups) and endangered species and the use and deployment digital tools and Artificial Intelligence (AI) in engaging marginalised and vulnerable groups and nonhuman actors. The Ethical Adviser has reviewed and commented these guidelines and will produce a report for each reporting period. Prior to reporting, the Ethical Adviser will meet up with WP-leaders about the past ethical challenges and future plans for each WP concerning the LL. Ethical Adviser will provide a lecture on ethical issues critical to the project, special emphasis being in the role and significance of marginalised and vulnerable groups and nonhuman actors in just coevolutionary transformation and in using of digital tools and artificial intelligence. An ethical Adviser may be invited, and he may suggest visits to project meetings and thematic symposiums when reasons emerge. The working process and principles of Ethical Adviser will be agreed (D8.1) upon in tandem with the detailed project work plan at M3.

5.3. Transparency and accountability

Open-access and transparent data management system will ensure that all stakeholders will have access to information about the project and its outcomes for example through the website and Zenodo. This information includes the project's goals, design, implementation, desired products, and expected outcome towards resolving the problem encountered and sustainable transformation. As for the transparency and accountability related to the Data collected is defined in the Data management plan.

5.4. Monitoring, assessment, and further development of ethical practices

Research ethics are dynamic, case and place specific and sensitive, not rigidly fixed. The ethical principles presented in this document provide a general framework for how we should work overall, but ethical working always involves decisions about what we should do in a particular context. A clear procedure for making those decisions is an important addition to these principles. Timewise ethical attention is needed throughout the whole research process, from the planning phase of the project to the start and implementation, until to the impacts of the completed project. “In relation to unanticipated outcomes or consequences of co-creative actions, it is crucial for living labs to establish contingency plans. Given that Living Labs facilitate the co-creation of nature-based solutions, they are well-suited to formulate supplementary contingency plans alongside their primary action plans. It is recommended that all Living Labs share their experiences concerning unforeseen effects and consequences arising from their respective actions, thereby enhancing the overall action plan within the COEVOLVERS framework.

The general ethical principles provided by the EU and national ethics committees and organisations (Chapter 3), the anticipated ethical principles associated especially to our project (Chapter 4), and new emerging ethical issues will be monitored and assessed, and practices to deal with these issues will be further developed throughout the COEVOLVER project.

- **Monitoring:** Each LL Core Group will review this document, discuss and co-design ethical guidelines with a checklist for their respective LL as a part of their Action plans. Using these guidelines and the checklist they will regularly monitor and assess the fulfilment of the principles and guidelines, including the of impacts of the NBS to humans and nonhumans, as well as the additional, unexpected ethical issues arising, document any deviations and observations and lessons learnt in different phases of the project (at the start/planning and engaging, during the activities, and towards the end) with a special focus on vulnerable and marginalised people and human - nonhuman aspects. The LL leaders/teams, on behalf of the LL Core Group, report back to the WP1/Living Lab meetings.
- **Solving emerging problematic situations:** The emerging situated ethical issues in different phases of the project implementation (at the start/planning and engaging, during the activities, and towards the end) will be identified and documented by the LL Teams. In case of difficult ethical problems, solutions will be sought for in the first place at the Living Labs, and when necessary and requested with the support through consultation by e.g. other Living Lab teams, Ethical Advisor and project co-ordinators.
- **Sharing and learning:** The reports from the LLs concerning the monitoring and new emerging issues as well as handling problematic situations will provide material for joint learning and co-developing best practices for dealing with various ethical issues in co-creating NBS. This material will used to assessed in respect to this document, and the final observations will be shared in the end of the project.

ANNEXES:

ANNEX I: List of ethical codes and guidelines

List of ethical codes and guidelines established in each partner country and/or by their institution.

Participant	Country	Organisation/Committee	Relevant guidelines and regulations (year)	Link
LUKE & City of Turku	Finland	The Finnish Advisory Board on Research Integrity (TENK)	The ethical principles of research with human participants and ethical review in the human sciences in Finland (2019)	https://tenk.fi/sites/default/files/2021-01/Ethical_review_in_human_sciences_2020.pdf
University of Erfurt	Germany	DFG Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft https://www.dfg.de/en/index.jsp	Scientists at the University of Erfurt are obliged to conduct their research on the basis of the "Guidelines for Safeguarding Good Research Practice" of the DFG (2019)	https://www.dfg.de/download/pdf/foerderung/rechtliche_rahmenbedingungen/gute_wissenschaftliche_praxis/kodex_gwp_en.pdf
University of Cagliari, Unica	Italy	1) Ministry of University and Research (MUR) 2) University of Cagliari (UNICA) 3) Italian Association of Psychology (AIP) 4) National Board of Italian Psychologists	1) National law (2010) 2) Ethics code of the University (2009 and subsequent amendments); Ethics committee University of Cagliari (2016); UNICA is under final evaluation by the European Community for the Human Resources Excellence in Research award (HRS4R) (2022) 3) Ethical Code of the Italian Association of Psychology (AIP) 4) National Board of Italian Psychologists Code of Ethics; WMA DECLARATION OF HELSINKI – ETHICAL PRINCIPLES FOR MEDICAL RESEARCH INVOLVING HUMAN SUBJECTS	1) https://www.parlamento.it/parlam/leggi/10240l.htm 2) https://www.unica.it/static/resources/cms/documents/Codice_adottato_DR.pdf ; https://www.unica.it/unica/it/ateneo_s01_ss04_sss02.page ; https://www.unica.it/unica/it/hrs4rstrategy.page 3) https://aipass.org/en/chi-siamo/#ethical-code 4) https://www.psy.it/la-professione-psicologica/codice-deontologico-degli-psicologi-italiani/ ; https://www.wma.net/policies-post/wma-declaration-of-helsinki-ethical-principles-for-medical-research-involving-human-subjects/#:~:text=The%20World%20Medical%20Association%20(WMA,identifiable%20human%20material%20and%20data.
Institute of Forest Ecology, Slovak Academy of Science, IFE SAS	Slovakia	Ethics commission of the Slovak Academy of Sciences: https://www.sav.sk/?lang=sk&doc=sas-commission&commission_no=16	SAS Code of Ethics	https://www.sav.sk/?lang=sk&doc=sas-commission&folder_no=141
Environmental Social Science Research Group, ESSRG & Maghaz	Hungary	Hungarian Academy of Sciences Medical Research Council	Science Ethics Code (2010) Codes of Bioethics (2016)	https://mta.hu/data/dokumentumok/english/background/Science_Ethics_Code_English.pdf https://ett.aeek.hu/en/secretariat/ https://ett.aeek.hu/en/codex-of-bioethics/
University of Tartu, UTARTU	Estonia	Research Ethics Committee of the University of Tartu https://ut.ee/en/node/113848 (there is no national institution)	Statute of the Research Ethics Committee of the University of Tartu (2011)	www.vana.ut.ee
Forest Science and Technology Centre Catalonia	Spain	Committee for Ethics in research (CERec)	CEEAH regulation (2017)	efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcqlclefindmkaj/https://www.uab.cat/doc/Reglament_CEEAH
James Hutton Institute, HUTTON	United Kingdom	Social Research Association	Research Ethics Guidance	https://the-sra.org.uk/SRA/SRA/Ethics/Ethics.aspx
CETIP	Czechia	Committee for Ethics in research works of the Czech Academy of Sciences https://www.avcr.cz/cs/onas/struktura/komise-pro-etiku-vedecke-prace/	Code of Ethics for Researchers of the Czech Academy of Sciences	https://www.avcr.cz/en/about-us/legal-regulations/code-of-ethics-for-researchers-of-the-czech-academy-of-sciences/

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No101084220. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

ANNEX II Info sheet

This is a two-pager info sheet that we agreed about to introduce the project to the stakeholders involved in the LLs and to be used when informing people about the project. The first page describes the project as a whole, while the second page focuses on the respective Living Lab. Here we use Turku Pansio-Perno Living Lab as a draft example. Please, describe the aim and main activities in your own LL emphasizing its specificities and translate the whole document to the local language. Try use language accessible to all participants.

There is an urgent call for solutions that concern the everyday life of citizens, their well-being and quality of life, and that could support their activities related to climate change and biodiversity loss. **Nature-based solutions (NBS)** are solutions that benefit both nature and humans, such as green roofs or wetlands. However, until now they are often only technical efforts, and not enough attention has been paid to the societal issues, local communities and citizens, or other species, who are the true beneficiaries of these solutions. COEVOLVERS – project (Coevolutionary approach to unlock the transformative potential of nature-based solutions for more inclusive and resilient communities) is a four-year project funded by the Horizon Europe programme (2022-2025) and co-ordinated by Natural Resources Institute Finland (Luke). [add the logos in the bottom of the page]

Together with seven different communities, **Living Labs**, across Europe (see the Figure 2.), the eleven partner organisations of COEVOLVERS -project explores new type of practices and governance models, and co-creates Nature-based solutions that help the local communities to adapt and contribute to the societal and environmental change.

The problems tackled are very diverse: e.g. loneliness in Scotland, wildfires in Catalonia, mental health rehabilitation in Hungary, or water shortage across Czechia and Slovakia border.

Figure 2. COEVOLVERS Living Labs

With innovative use of various digital tools and creative methods, these problems are explored and analysed together with local communities. Finally practices and tools for more inclusive and just governance are designed.

In order to do this, each Living Lab invites representatives of local communities including municipalities, NGOs and other organized actors for collaboration. Furthermore, individual citizens play a key role in the different phases of the project. During a forthcoming years different Living Labs also organize joint activities, which enables exchange of knowledge and mutual learning also across countries and societies.

Pansio-Perno, Turku, Finland - Greening post-industrial suburb

Why and to whom?

City growth usually happens on green areas, which reduces their quality and connectivity, having harmful impacts on humans and urban ecosystems. The Pansio-Perno neighbourhood is presently under detailed zoning, and a target of complementary construction, which poses a threat to local green space. Fifth of its residents speak languages other than Finnish or Swedish and have low-income levels, while education level is lower and unemployment higher than in Turku in general. The target group of the Living Lab is the residents of the neighbourhood.

What? (the aim)

One current solution for addressing weakening urban ecosystem health and biodiversity loss is ecological compensation. Lost nature values are compensated in another place applying a no-net-loss principle, meaning that total natural values remain at least on the current level. However, ecological compensation is inert to what social, cultural and experiential values are attached to green spaces by residents and hence it tends to maintain and even increase social conflict. The Living Lab aims to co-develop socio-ecological compensation to incorporate social, cultural and experiential values of urban nature.

How? (in practice)

Pansio-Perno Living Lab will work in neighbourhood-level to coordinate a design and test process for socio-ecological compensation. The Living Lab will use various participatory methods and citizen science to engage with the residents, starting with an online survey to map experiences and beliefs about the socio-politics of NBS. Other methods include visual tools like Photovoice, learning diaries, interviews, workshops, social media.

Impact (what are the benefits/advantages)

This Living Lab demonstrates NBS that engages the residents into the land use and neighbourhood planning. The goal is to ensure the inclusive no-net-loss compensation approach to safeguard nature and human values of urban environments

ANNEX III. Plain language document

Use this document as a basis when providing more accurate information about the participation and data collection, and before asking the consent form.

Communities and societies across Europe increasingly face societal and ecological challenges caused by climate change and biodiversity loss. Nature-based Solutions (NBS) are generally understood as solutions that are inspired and supported by nature, which are cost-effective, simultaneously provide environmental, social and economic benefits and help build resilience. Solutions, such as green roofs, rain gardens or constructed wetlands may bring more and more diverse nature and natural features and processes into cities, landscapes and seascapes. Although the NBS are gaining attention, they have not been able to sufficiently involve in the planning and implementation those, who are most vulnerable and have marginalized position, nor benefit nature in the long term. For these reasons the NBS are not necessarily able to advance the overall resilience of the communities and transformation to sustainability.

You are invited to participate in the activities of COEVOLVERS -project (Coevolutionary approach to unlock the transformative potential of nature-based solutions for more inclusive and resilient communities funded by Horizon Europe Programme (Grant n:o 101084220). COEVOLVERS -project holds that NBS need to be better connected with the everyday practices of the various social groups and nonhumans (e.g. individual species, representatives of species, ecosystems, habitats, populations, physical structures, material substance) modes of life. These solutions are developed in seven communities, so-called Living Labs, across Europe together with local citizen governmental organisations, companies, individual citizens responding to locally specific challenges. In [name of your LL] the focus will be on [name the preliminary challenge and solution identified].

The project is led by the Natural Resources Institute Finland (Luke) in collaboration with [your institute] and seven other partners. The activities will be carried out in agreement and cooperation with [name local partners] and will bring together participants with different understandings and priorities regarding the local challenge and the potential solutions.

You are invited to participate in the project activities as we believe that you could contribute to the collaborative work based on your interest, experience and/or knowledge of the topic. Accepting to participate may mean the following:

- participating in one or more project activities (workshops; meetings);
- contributing to data collection e.g. answering questionnaires, interviews etc. concerning the activities (before, during and/or after).

As a participant you will

- have an opportunity to learn and share your experience and knowledge of the topic;
- have opportunities for discussion and networking with other local actors;
- learn from the other Living Labs involved in the project.

We hope that you are interested in participating in many of the LL activities, you can freely choose the activities and you can also withdraw from participation at any time [you may add information on how and when]. Information (such as interviews, questionnaires) and other materials (photos, videos, drawings) collected during the activities will be used as a basis for reports, scientific articles and possibly in other contexts such as websites or exhibitions. Data will be stored by the research team and may be used as a basis for future studies. Your personal data will be handled in accordance with the EU Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [set a link to your national GDPR -site]. You will receive a detailed description of your role as a participant, as well as data collection and analysis and use, prior any activity starts.

ANNEX IV. Consent form

Use this form as basis and modify the different items relevant to your activity and participant.

RESEARCH CONSENT FORM

Name of Researcher(s)
Title of the study
Coevolutionary approach to unlock the transformative potential of nature-based solutions for more inclusive and resilient communities (COEVOLVERS)

- I have had the research satisfactorily explained to me in verbal and written form by the researcher. **YES / NO**
- I understand that the research will involve: *interviews, surveys, art-based methods...* (add here the activities/methods you are planning to use) **YES / NO**
- I understand that I may withdraw from this study at any time without having to give an explanation. **YES / NO**
- I understand that all information about me will be treated in strict confidence and that I will not be named in any written work arising from this study. **YES / NO**
- I understand that my personal data will be collected, processed and stored as described in the data protection notice described to me orally and that the information is also to be found on the web following this link: *xxx* (add here a link to the data protection number) **YES / NO**

Attached is a description of the study.

I freely give my consent to participate in this research study.

Name:

Signature:

Date:

ANNEX V: Follow-up on ethical issues (M6-M18)

Introduction

In COEVOLVERS, implementation of the ethical guidelines will be monitored, and supportive activities like additional training and consultation of the Ethical advisor will be arranged when needed (D1.1., Chapter 5). This Annex reports ethical issues that have been faced in the Living Labs and in the project more broadly after the submission of the ethical guidelines (M6), and how they have been addressed or resolved. The report is a live document that will be updated in every reporting period until the end of the project.

Follow up on ethical issues (M 6 – 18)

Continuous follow up and support

Living Labs have been advised to follow and discuss ethical matters related to their activities and without hesitation raise any ethical concern they have faced in the bi-weekly LL meetings or in the one-to-one meetings between LL teams and WP1. In these meetings, no major ethical issues were reported. Concerns were practical, mostly related to the format, use of the consent forms or other GSDR -related issues. Training on how to discuss and handle ethical issues were arranged in a kick-off meeting and ethical considerations related to in-depth interviews and survey (Task 4.1.) was organised. Ethical guidelines were also attached to the interview guide (Task 4.1.). Research ethics and ethical matters related to our topic were discussed on regular basis in our project meetings.

Workshop on ethical issues at the project level (M 13)

A workshop on ethical issues, as a part of the bi-weekly project meeting, was arranged on December 5, 2023. The event was for all partners and researchers of the consortium. The aim was to map and collect any ethical issues either in research topic or practice raised or encountered by the LLs and WPs during the first year of the project. The workshop participants discussed following topics in two groups: 1) What kind of ethical issues have you encountered regarding i) the general ethical principles set by the European Commission and national ethics committees (e.g. consent forms, minors, etc), ii) specificities of COEVOLVERS co-creation process (e.g. inclusivity of vulnerable people, non-humans, language), and iii) data collection and management; and 2) Which of the issues would require further actions and support for solving them. The results of the discussions were shared in a joint session. Three main groups of topics were identified: 1) inclusivity – human actors; 2) inclusivity – non-human actors; and 3) data collection and management especially in relation to GDPR (See table 1.).

The identified topics were briefly presented and discussed in an online meeting on February 13, 2024, before sending them out to project's Ethical Advisor, Senior lecturer Markku Oksanen. The Ethical Advisor joined the project's biweekly meeting on February 27 to discuss about raised ethical issues with the consortium. The list of the identified topics was sent to him

in advance (Table 1). Below we summarise the key issues from Oksanen’s presentation and the discussion.

Table 1. Ethical issues encountered by the LLs and WPs

Topic 1: Inclusivity – human actors	Potential actions
Identification of vulnerable and marginalized people/groups (in NBS design and implementation)?	Stakeholder mapping and analysis Vulnerability as a theme in Reader’s teatime with our new advisory board member Marja-Liisa Honkasalo
Different levels of participation (in NBS design and implementation)	Stakeholder mapping and analysis
Challenges in translation when working with diversity of the participants/practitioners in co-creation	Readers’ teatime and glossary on the keywords with scientific and layman versions
Engaging different type of stakeholders in co-creation) - how to involve quiet participants? - how to involve those who are “important”, but not interested in? - is it possible to exclude someone for some reasons? When and how?	A LL session on these topics Julia’s report on the co-creation methods + mapping additional techniques
Topic 2. inclusivity – non-human actors	Potential actions
How to—“involve” non-humans? Is it right to represent non-humans?	”Ecocentric democracy and issue related to language” work in progress by Carsten and Simo
How do we know who are communicating non-humans’ views?	
How to identify/assess possible negative and positive impacts of our work on the non-humans?	
What are the rights of animals/non-humans in the new NBS?	
Topic 3: data management in relation to GDPR	Potential actions
Sessions with children and patients (permissions, consent forms, dissemination practices)	A project meeting dedicated to these issues.
Ensuring anonymity of the interviewees in publications	
Participants, who are not concerned with the anonymity, participants who leave the project	
Sharing transcripts of audio files within the consortium	

Research ethics

Overall, when discussing the research ethics, we do not face major issues. As for the research ethics in data collection and management, the ethical advisor reminded that a consent gained needs to be within the GDPR, which is compelling legislation in all European countries. Also when transferring data across borders, we need to make sure that there is no clash with the national regulation, ownership issues or privacy. Always consult a lawyer or a legal expert, if there are issues that we are uncertain about. The Steering Committee confirmed that in order to underline the importance of the ethical issues in our work we will include the ethical issues in every meeting agenda.

Meeting with Ethical Advisor (Month 16)*Inclusive language*

The concept of Living Lab is scientific or expert driven concept. Although the concept is defined on the project website, the meaning of it is not necessarily clear to all the participants of the Living lab activities. It was also noted that it is not necessarily easy to translate the term Living Lab to any local language. Many of the LLs do not use it when working with their stakeholders, because they have realized it may confuse although the idea of the collaborative research as such is clearer to the project participants and stakeholders. COEVOLVERS will work on the layman definition for the Living Lab concept (WP1).

Situation is the same with the concept “vulnerable and marginalised people”. Conceptualizing individual people as vulnerable or marginalised may stigmatise and strengthen conditions of produce vulnerability. For example, immigrants may not always be vulnerable or marginalised: they may live in a foreign country on voluntary basis or temporarily. It was discussed that instead of stigmatizing individual people, social groups, or non-humans as vulnerable, we may focus on socio-political conditions that produce vulnerability and make people or other species vulnerable. Thus, the key question for the COEVOLVERS is how to change the conditions to make them less vulnerable and strengthen for instance empowerment and capabilities. Vulnerability becomes a holistic notion: an individual does not necessarily feel or identify him/herself as vulnerable, but an external expert may realize that the living conditions are or may become such that make them vulnerable. It was also suggested that vulnerability is a leeway to adapt: If you notice that options become narrower in the future, but you do not have opportunities to adapt you may become vulnerable.

Ethics in relation to other species and their living environments

The basic principle in the research ethics is that researchers should not do any (significant) harm to animal or plant species, nor ecosystems. The current ethical rules apply primarily to laboratory animals or farm animals. In environmental ethics, discussion revolves around the

institutional position (e.g. rights) of wild plants, animal species and ecosystems which is a more controversial and complex issue. Wellbeing of other than human species, especially plants, can be considered as a scientific construct and expert opinion is needed to better understand what non-humans need to flourish. Yet, in practice, rights of animals and elimination of invasive species may arise conflicts from the individual species point of view. This is a long-standing question in environmental philosophy. There are obnoxious animals, animals that may cause harm to biodiversity (e.g. white-tailed deer) or to humans (e.g. ticks, rats). It was also noted that COEVOLVERS may avoid many problems, as we consider non-humans having agency in the co-creation and co-evolution of NBS. As a conclusion we agreed that there should not be strict opposition between researchers and non-humans; rather, we try to create a dialogical relation with them. Therefore, many questions researchers normally face when working with animals and other living organisms do not concern us.

Environmental, ecological and ecocentric democracy are getting more and more attention and will also be explored by WP2 in COEVOLVERS. Their principles in relation to our project were also discussed especially how the animals, plants and ecosystems can be presented. For example, it was mentioned that in Ecuador anyone can represent nature and sue on behalf of nature, while in the *ombudsman* system the representation is legally based. It was noted that while the idea of the ecological democracy could be supported, it may arise some practical challenges. Having representatives for plants, animals or ecosystems may also arise some problems, as there are a number of individual animals or plants and species and ecosystems. It is not possible to acquire every individual imagined opinion from single-cell organisms to big trees and animals. The non-humans may also have different needs and interests, which may be in clash. Therefore, it was suggested that different kind of democracy is needed for non-humans.

Meeting with Advisory Board member on rethinking vulnerability (M17)

As the issue of vulnerability raised many questions and concerns, we invited our advisory board member emerita professor Marja-Liisa Honkasalo (University of Turku, University of Helsinki) to visit our consortium meeting.

Marja-Liisa Honkasalo gave a thorough presentation on the concept of vulnerability based on her article on the topic from an interdisciplinary perspective and reflecting the COEVOLVERS project aim and context. She dwelled through the etymology and different (and sometimes even controversial) meanings of vulnerability in different contexts and finally some potential applications in the NBS research and COEVOLVERS project. These included both methodological (such as effects of the interventions) as well as vulnerability as a window to recognize and explore the multiple relations and ways to consent.

Engaging with the Advisory Board members and the Ethical Advisory in the COEVOLVERS annual Consortium Meeting (M18)

In the consortium meeting in Cagliari, Italy, 22-24.4.2024 the discussion around multispecies justice and vulnerability continued in a dialogue with the Living Labs. Advisory members prof. Christopher Raymond and prof. emerita Marja-Liisa Honkasalo gave short introductions to multispecies justice and vulnerability, respectively. The discussion revolved around the conflicts around animal species that were considered as harmful, or native species as well as how to deal with the concept of vulnerability and avoid using power by defining people vulnerable or non-vulnerable.

Following the multispecies approach, we should aim for engaging also vulnerable and non-humans. On the other hand, if we aim to engage with all stakeholders including all other species, all stakeholders are in an equal position, and we are in a situation to empower those who are in a vulnerable position. The second topic concerned inclusivity of the language. The language humans speak is not shared by other species, should we use other signs for communication? Could NBS be such a sign? NBS changes the physical environment, which the non-humans have to adapt to. In this way the NBS could be a means of communication between humans and non-humans. It was also noted that by designing and implementing NBS and even using the concept of “multispecies” we easily construct new relations and hierarchies between humans, and between and non-humans, of which we need to be aware of.